

Cfd Simulation of Passive Base Drag Control in Missiles

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Abstract

Achieving the planned trajectory is a key factor to aid a successful missile mission. One of the factors is the generation of base drag which is responsible for the deviations in trajectory and this will leads to imbalance stability or loss of flight stability. This work focuses about the implementation of passive control techniques that incorporate the effect of slots to the missile aft body. Numerical simulations are carried out by employing various case of study with OPEN-FOAM. For reducing the effect of base drag on the missile, shape modifications are employed by means of attaching rectangular slots in 3 different angles 0° , $+7^{\circ}$, -7° . The results are compared with conventional solver out- put and an inference is made from these observations.

Keywords: Base drag, trajectory, passive control, OPEN- FOAM.

1. INTRODUCTION

The major factor which corresponds to the deviation in trajectory of the missile mission is the generation of base drag. A partial vacuum created in the rockets tail region is the corresponding base drag which is a component of aerodynamic drag. The tremendous volume of gas generated while the motor is firing will fills the void which reduces the drag. Once the gas is disappeared this drag takes a sharp jump at burnout. The owe at the aft end of projectile is characterized by higher amount of unsteadiness and increased drag due to reduction in base pressure. This drag is termed as base drag. Methods in use for reduction of the base drag are as follows:

- Boat tailing of the base
- Base bleed through the projectile body
- Use of aerodynamic fins

The modification used in the work is the attachment of rectangular tabs on the periphery of the base body in the projectile. Introducing tabs at the tail passively controls the base pressure by introducing stream wise vortices. The discontinuity in the tab structure will be the source of the introduction of the stream wise vortices. The angle of the tab will also alter its effect on the control of base pressure and the associated base drag.

2. CFD Simulation

The projectile body G7 is taken as reference and is modified in the base with the attachment of rectangular tabs in three orientations (0° , $+7^{\circ}$, -7°). The missile is set to be tested in with steady flow using the K –SST turbulence model for compressible flow with supersonic mach of 2 along with an ambient pressure of 101325 Pa. The density based solvers are used in fluent for this kind of simulations and in OpenFOAM, RHOSIMPLEFOAM will be used

3. PROCESS AND PROCEDURE

Geometry

Parent specimen G7 projectile is taken as the standard boat- tailed projectile body and the base is modified into base tabs. Both the original specimen and the modifications are modeled in Catia V5 software. The Geometry is exported as iges files into Ansys Workbench 15.0- Design Modeler. In the Design Modeler, the geometry is enclosed with a cylinder domain with the nose of projectile facing the flow. The body is made as a cavity by the Boolean-Subtract feature. The Aft-Body

involves placement of 10 Rectangular Tabs along the periphery of the base at 0° , $+7^{\circ}$, -7° .

Figure 1: Geometry

4. MESH

The meshing is done through Workbench 15.0 Meshing. The meshing is predominantly structured except for the intricate parts of the structure. The tabs structure is meshed with smaller control for effective domain and solid boundary generation. The boundaries and named selections are promptly specified for the ease of solving. The projectile body is taken as solid by default. The complete mesh is exported as .msh (ascii) and is made to run on both solvers.

Figure 2: Mesh

5. SOLVING IN FLUENT

The domain is modeled to desired flow conditions and is executed through fluent preprocessing. The Fluent 15.0 enables the user to input the parameters and models for the specific case. The boundary conditions are very integral part of CFD as it determines the establishment of the flow properties to the appropriate regions. The inlet and outlet are pressure based conditions while the walls of domain are given symmetry. The velocity and pressure values are also computed from the inlet and set for initialization. With respect to this criteria the gauge pressure is set to 12949 Pa and velocity as 695 m/s

6. SOLVING IN OPENFOAM

The pre-processing in Openfoam is done using Helyx OS. It is a GUI and is capable of creating

appropriate case directories for specified case. The .msh file is imported into the module and is incorporated as Openfoam Case directory by the command `fluentMeshToFoam ;name;.msh`. Then the case is reopened and the model specifications similar to those given in the conventional solver are given through the GUI. Open- FOAM uses `rhoSimpleFoam` solver for the given models and executes the iterations up to specified limit. The time directory stores the results of solution.

7. POSTPROCESSING

The Post processing interface in fluent constitutes of features to display the contours of flow parameters over the body, plots, graphics and various other formats to infer the results. The Pressure plot is the significant result for many studies. The post processing GUI of OpenFoam can be opened by typing `paraFoam` command in the terminal of the case directory folder. The interface is equally equipped as fluent and is extensively adaptive to new features.

8. RESULTS

Figure 3: Boat tail Static Pressure (Ansys)

Figure 3: Boat tail with tabs Static Pressure (Ansys)

Figure 4: Boat tail Static Pressure (Openfoam)

Figure 5: Boat tail with tabs Static Pressure (Openfoam)

The body is set in ambient pressure of 12949 Pa. The tip experiences heavy stagnation pressure and oblique shocks due which pressure peaks high as 6500 Pa at the nose tip. Due to the shock wave the fore body experiences pressure hike until flow reaches the neck after which the expansion fans expand the flow in stages. The aft body modifications contribute to variation in the expansion and thus help in base drag reduction. Since the base drag coefficient is effectively depending on the ratio of base pressure to ambient pressure, it's essential to implement a modification that shall influence the ratio effectively. The boat tail shape is experiencing a back pressure of 0.07 bars and hence is implied to cause a higher base drag than the tabs. Among the tabs, the positive tabs seem to be the most effective one as that contributed a huge pressure recovery among the models. The drag coefficient is found to be a function of the back pressure and it has been observed that at the boat tail model it is 0.45. Moreover for the neural, positive and negative tabs model gives the parameters of 0.5, 0.55 and 0.4 respectively.

9. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The hypothesis states that base tabs can be more effective than base boat tailing is inferred as false from the above observation. The use of tabs in base is not as effective as boat tailing as it incurs more drag. But considering the observation that the negative oriented tabs are quite effective than boat tail configurations which means the case can overcome the drawbacks of boat tail.

The case is not exactly similar to the fluent case, yet is reflecting similar inference as in the compressible case that is the negative tabs are effective than positively oriented ones because it produces lesser pressure recovery which in turn reduces the base drag. The work is continued towards simulating compressible flow in the OpenFOAM module through deeper CFD studies and generation of codes to create specific solver that can effectively reflect the results of the conventional software.

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